

The Effect of Work Involvement on the Readiness to Change at PT. Mutifa Medan

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Abstract— This study was to determine the impact of work involvement toward readiness to change in PT. Mutifa Medan. Data of the study was obtained through a scale of work involvement and a scale of readiness to change that has been tested for reliability and validity. The subjects of this study were 215 employees in PT. Mutifa Medan. The results showed that there is positive impact of work involvement on readiness to change of employee in PT. Mutifa Medan. The meaning is, the more involved the employees in the company, the more ready they are to change. And vice versa, if the work involvement decreases, the level of readiness to change also decreases. The results of the study are expected to be an input for the company to increase readiness to change on their employee through work involvement.

Keywords— Readiness to change, work involvement, PT. Mutifa Medan.

I. INTRODUCTION

Changes in a company are inevitable, both large and small scale changes. Changes occur due to several factors such as changes in technology, competition, business paradigms, economics, globalization, consumer tastes and workforce composition (Robbins & Judge, 2011). Developments and competition in the industrial world encourage companies to be ready to face the dynamics of environmental change. This condition requires the company to be able to adapt to changes that occur, because these changes cannot be avoided by companies if they want to develop. Changes in the organization resulted in the shifting of a condition that prevails in the organization today, leading to the desired future conditions in order to increase its effectiveness (Winardi, 2010).

Changes made in a company have several objectives including to improve the effectiveness of the company, and develop the potential of employees in a company (George & Jones, 2012). A change becomes something that needs to be implemented by every company that wants to develop. The development of a company will be increasingly demanded to continue to innovate and change in order to keep abreast of developments and be able to compete with other companies (Tohidi, 2012). Correspondingly, Gunawan, Suryono, and Purwanto (2010), said that there are two factors that require a company to make changes, namely internal factors (internal problems) and external (external problems).

Readiness to change into an evaluation phase carried out for individuals as a whole and conclude that the individual is ready for the changes that occur (Rafferty, & Jimmieson 2013). Companies that succeed in making changes when employees also have goals to change, have plans to change, and become part of these changes (Bridges, 2009). Thus, one

thing that also has an important role in organizational change is individuals who are part of the organization (Robbins, 2013). Organizational change will not succeed without giving employees the opportunity to make changes and changes made to be ineffective without being prepared in advance (Shum, Bove & Auh, 2010).

It is important for organizations to continually understand that the organization does not only focus on emerging technology issues, intense market competition, and the ever-changing business environment, but pay attention to the influence of employees' attitudes toward these changes (Shum, et al., 2010). If examined further, Maheswari and Vohra (2015) also revealed that one of the most frequently cited reasons for the failure to implement change was that the organization did not adequately handle problems related to human resources. Managing organizational change can be done by managing employees involved in the process of organizational change because employees are sources and tools for change (Keith, 2012).

Lack of individual readiness to change will affect the success of the organization to change. Individual readiness to change in the process of organizational change is very important and needed, both from the perspective of employees in consolidating the changes that occur and in terms of the success of changes in the future (Mangundjaya, 2016). The management in the company should understand that success in improving quality and productivity must involve employees because employees are not only a major force in bringing about change, but also increasingly actively participating in planning changes (Robbins & Judge, 2011).

One of the factors that is expected to influence readiness to change is work involvement. According to Abdallah, Obeidat, Aqqad, Janini, and Dahiyat (2017), agreed that work involvement is a major supporting factor in the success of an organization. Thus explaining that work involvement is closely related to what is felt by employees of their work which will affect the achievement of the organization. According to Safaria (2013), that work involvement has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. Correspondingly, Ciliana and Mansoer (2008) found that there was an influence of work involvement, work stress and organizational commitment on employee readiness to change. This shows that individuals who are actively involved in the organization have a higher readiness to change than individuals who are passively involved. Individuals who are actively involved in the organization will also have a fairly high involvement in their work.

Lodahl and Kejner (in Aryaningtyas, 2013), revealed that work involvement can be seen from the extent to which a person identifies psychologically with his work or the importance of work in an individual's self-image. In this theory emphasizes that every member of the organization must actively participate in work as the most important part that embodies his self-image. Directing companies toward change requires management and all employees' support (Holt, Armenakis & Harris, 2007). Work involvement is considered necessary to be owned by employees because it is important for the employee's self-concept in the company in placing work as an important part of his life (Sharma, 2016).

One example of companies that make changes to develop for the better is PT. Mutifa where this company is one of the pharmaceutical industry companies in Indonesia. PT. Mutiara Mukti Farma (MUTIFA) is one of the companies engaged in the production of medicines. In 1983, the company was established and carried out its operations in producing various types and forms of drug preparations to meet the needs of the people of North Sumatra in particular. In accordance with the Decree of the Minister of Health RI No. 43 / Menkes / SK / II / 1988 concerning pharmaceutical companies, PT. Mutifa has followed the Guidelines for Making Good Medicines (CPOB) from the Ministry of Health, namely the guidelines can improve the quality of pharmaceutical products continuously and provide better protection to public health.

Changes in PT.Mutifa along with the times and consumer needs. The changes made have proven successful by proving the stability of the company PT.Mutifa to date. The change itself is to make things different which leads to the desired conditions in the future. Various organizational development policies that have been carried out by PT.Mutifa in increasing the competitiveness of companies in the pharmaceutical market share. These changes have been responded well by management so that the company's performance remains positive and sustainable in the future. PT. Mutifa makes the concept of change that is not spared from human resources who are ready to make changes and the involvement of employees in work as well as the people who accept the changes in production at PT. Mutifa. Achieving the company's goals at PT.Mutifa requires cooperation from all parties who are members of the company for the smooth running of the activities of an organization.

As part of the company, employees at PT.Mutifa as individuals who helped prepare themselves to face the implementation of change. PT. Mutifa expects a pattern of progress in the form of employee involvement in working for the purpose of organizational change and development which in the implementation of its work can be facilitated by leaders who have an active role in changing the company so that employees show interest in wanting to provide their capacity for the implementation of the work process to be provided. For that reason, in facilitating the process of change within the company, leaders can act to ensure that the performance of employees is ready to be changed and involved in changes in the company.

Based on the things described above, the researchers want to know and want to see the effect of work involvement on readiness to change of employee in PT. Mutifa Medan.

II. OBJECTIVES AND METHODS

The main purpose of this study was to see the effect of work involvement on readiness to change of employee in PT. Mutifa Medan. The subjects of this study were 215 employee in PT. Mutifa Medan. Data of the study was obtained through a scale of work involvement and a scale of readiness to change that has been tested for reliability and validity. The work involvement scale is based on four dimensions of work involvement according theory from Luthans (2006). The dimensions are main interests in life, active participation in work, performance as important for self and regard performance consistent with self concepts. Work involvement scale consists of 13 item statements with a reliability level of 0.860.

The readiness to change scale is based on four dimensions of readiness to change according theory from Holt, Field and Armenakis (2007). The dimensions are appropriateness, change specific efficacy, management support and personal valence. Readiness to change scale consists of 17 item statements with a reliability level of 0.921. The work involvement scale and readiness to change scale used a Likert scale model with five alternative answer choices: 1 (strongly disagree), 2 (disagree), 3 (neutral), 4 (agree), 5 (strongly agree). Scores for each item correspond to the answers given by the subject. However, on some items in negative statements, the opposite score applies. In this study the analytical method used is simple regression method.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study the hypothesis given is that there is an influence of work involvement on readiness to change in PT. Mutifa Medan. In this study the method of analysis used is simple regression method. From the results of data collection on 215 employee in PT. Mutifa Medan has produce the following statistical values:

TABLE I. Regression Result

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	F	Sig.
Regression	18090.156	1	389.855	.000
Residual	9883.677	213		
Total	27973.833	214		

Based on the results of the analysis above, a significance value of 0.00 (F arithmetic = 389.855, $p < .05$), indicates that the hypothesis is accepted. It means there is a significant influence of work involvement on readiness to change.

Further data analysis is performed to see the effective contribution of work involvement to readiness to change. The amount of contributions can be seen from the table below:

TABLE II. R Regression Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of The Estimate
1	0.804	.647	.645	6.812

The table above shows the value of the correlation coefficient (R) of .804 and the value of the determinant coefficient (R Square) of .647. This value indicates that the effect of work involvement on readiness to change is 64.7%, while the rest (35.3%) is caused by other factors not examined

in this study.

Further analysis is carried out to see the regression equation between work involvement to readiness to change, which can be seen from the following table:

TABLE III. Regression Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	8.750	2.948		2.968	.003
Work Involvement	1.143	.058	.804	19.745	.000

The regression equation is described by the formula $Y' = B_0 + B_1X_1$, where Y is readiness to change, while work involvement is denoted by X_1 . Based on the table above, the regression equation between work involvement and readiness to change is $Y' = 8.750 + 1.143 X_1$. A constant value of 8.750 indicates that if employee do not have work involvement, the readiness to change consistency value is 8.750. The regression coefficient shows the number 1.143. This means that if work involvement increases by 1%, then readiness to change increases by 1.143.

The equation above shows that the direction of influence given work involvement to readiness to change is a positive direction. This shows that the higher work involvement on their employee, the higher readiness to change in there, and vice versa. Based on the regression analysis it can be concluded that the hypothesis in this study was accepted which means there is a positive impact of work involvement on readiness to change in PT. Mutifa Medan.

Related to this, there is a discussion that can explain that the work involvement that is raised on employees at PT. Mutifa has a positive effect on readiness to change. The first reason, as mentioned by Graham (in Rahmadin, 2010) states that a person can have many attitudes towards certain objects or situations, but in this case it is limited to work-related, one of which relates to job involvement . The success of creating work involvement in a company is important to achieve the company's vision and mission. And this is where the company's role is to increase the work involvement of its employees to be more visible in their work, one of which can be by creating harmonious teamwork. Siegel and Hall (in Auliah, 2011) define work engagement as an attitude in which a person perceives that at work, employees find a sense of meaning for the job, the emergence of a feeling of security to do the job, and indicate availability to be able to do the job. The involvement of work done is a form of positive attitude on the job. Employees assume that a positive attitude at work will be shown fully in the physical, cognitive, and emotional roles of doing and completing tasks properly and responsibly. Because they realize that contributions made in work can help organizations to achieve the desired values and goals.

As stated by Blau & Boal (in Kartiningsih, 2010) work involvement implies a positive and complete statement from the core aspects of oneself at work. Work involvement will make a person can put out his best ability to do the job. Engagement contains tremendous potential for building and fostering teamwork. But in practice it is difficult to practice and can fail if not implemented properly. If involvement can

be put to good practice, the best results that can be generated are the readiness of employees to make changes (Davis & Newstrom, 2010).

The main driver of work engagement with employees is a sense of respect and feeling involved, the extent to which employees feel able to voice their ideas. In the condition of employees at PT. Mutifa company has aroused employee involvement in working one of them by communicating that they are required in their work to follow the changes that occur in the company and try to carry out according to the direction of the leadership in order to follow the implementation of the changes that occur. The work involvement shown from the employees starts from the acquisition of resource support for the completion of their work, then is given training in accordance with the objectives of the work to improve employee knowledge and skills.

Work involvement can make employees feel more welcome and involved in various situations in the organization so that their cooperation may also increase. Evidence shows that job involvement will be more successful if employees feel that they can contribute. And the results clearly show that work involvement has a broad system impact which is beneficial for the organization especially for showing the readiness of employees in facing organizational changes going forward.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded that there is positive impact of work involvement on readiness to change of employee in PT. Mutifa Medan. The implication is, the more involved the employees in the company, the more ready they are to change. And vice versa, if the work involvement decreases, the level of readiness to change also decreases. The results of this study can be input for all company, especially in PT. Mutifa Medan in order to consider work involvement as a factors to increasing the readiness to change on their employee. The implication of this resesearch can be used as a reference or guidance to PT. Mutifa Medan to making policy, planning and implementation strategy which can succeed in organizational change in their company which is being progress at this time.

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